

TENSILE FATIGUE DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT IN PLAIN WEAVE AND KNITTED FABRIC COMPOSITES (GFRP)

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SUMMARY: The tensile fatigue behavior of plain weave and knitted fabric composites has been investigated. Fatigue damage development in knitted fabric composites is quite different from that in plain-weave fabric composites. Fatigue damage in plain-weave fabric composites was initiated by transverse bundle cracking. Initial fatigue damage in knitted fabric composites was situated at the part of the curled bundle yarn that is perpendicular to the tensile loading direction. Regarding the relative residual stiffness, woven fabric composites show better fatigue resistance than knitted fabric composites. However, both woven and knitted fabric composites show comparable results in the fatigue life and the relative residual strength.

KEYWORDS: tensile fatigue, damage mechanism, knitted fabric composites, woven fabric composites, residual stiffness, residual strength.

INTRODUCTION

The use of textile fabrics has offered a lower cost to composite manufacturing and higher damage tolerance in impact loading. Woven, knitted, braided fabrics are textile fabrics that are widely used in many applications. Each type of these fabrics has advantages and disadvantages. Knitted fabric composites, for instance, have the highest deformability and impact resistance compared to braided and woven fabric composites [1-3]. However, the in-plane mechanical properties of woven fabric composites in the weft (filling) and warp directions are higher than those of knitted fabric composites.

In service, composite structures are often subjected not only to impact but also to fatigue loads. Fatigue loading creates fatigue damage which in turn decreases the in-plane mechanical properties of the composite (strength and stiffness). Therefore, it is important to investigate the fatigue behavior of textile composites. Tensile fatigue properties of glass-woven fabric composites in warp and weft direction have been reported in some references [4-7]. The failure mechanism in woven fabric composites is initiated by fiber-matrix debonds in

fiber bundles oriented transversely to the loading direction. In the main directions (weft/filling or warp direction), the final failure is strongly determined by the fiber bundles oriented longitudinal to the loading direction. The fatigue properties of woven fabric composites are also influenced by the stress concentrations around notches and holes and by the ductility of the matrix. On the other hand, there are not many publications on the tensile fatigue properties of knitted fabric composites. Shen Chou et al [8] investigated the flexural fatigue properties of weft knitted fabric composites compared to that of plain weave fabric composites. Plain weave fabric composites were reported having a higher flexural fatigue tolerance than knitted fabric composites. The nature of fatigue failure and the fatigue damage development were not discussed.

The objectives of this paper are to investigate and to compare tensile fatigue properties of knitted and woven fabric composites. This paper focuses on the fatigue damage development and the nature of the fatigue failure in correlation with the relative residual strength, the relative residual stiffness, and the fatigue life. E-glass-woven and E-glass-warp-knitted fabric composites were used. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), optical microscopy and acoustic emission (AE) were used to evaluate the fatigue damage.

EXPERIMENTS

Plain weave and knitted fabric composites were produced in an autoclave under hydrostatic pressure of 3 bar and a curing temperature of 125°C. Woven and knitted fabrics were impregnated using epoxy film F533 from Hexcel. Table 1 lists the average static tensile properties and fiber volume fraction of both textile fabric composites.

Properties	Knitted		Woven (Weft)
	Wale	Course	
Young's Modulus, E_x	9.1 ± 0.5 GPa	8.0 ± 0.5 GPa	20.0 ± 0.6 GPa
Tensile Strength, σ_{ult}	135.0 ± 5 MPa	102.0 ± 5 MPa	430.0 ± 10.0 MPa
Fiber volume fraction, %	30.0 ± 1.0 %	30.0 ± 1.0 %	50.0 ± 1.0 %

Table 1. Static tensile properties of knitted and woven fabric composites

Fatigue tests were performed on a Schenck fatigue machine. A constant load amplitude was kept during measurement. Fatigue tests were carried out at different maximum stress fatigue ratios S_{max} ($= \sigma_{max} / \sigma_{ult}$). Four maximum stress fatigue ratios, $S_{max} = 0.4, 0.5, 0.7$ and 0.9 were used. All tests were run at a stress ratio R ($\sigma_{min}/\sigma_{max}$) = 0.1 and at a frequency of 3 Hz. σ_{max} and σ_{min} are the maximum and minimum applied stresses respectively. σ_{ult} is the ultimate strength. The fatigue specimens had a width of 25 mm and a length of 230 mm. Aluminium end tabs with length of 40 mm, were attached at both ends of the specimen to avoid failure around the gripping device during the tests. The gauge length of the specimen was 150 mm. Two AE sensors were placed at the middle of the specimen. The area of the AE investigation was 30 % of the total area of specimens.

For the microscopic analysis, the fatigued specimens were cut and polished using silicon graphite paper with size of 4000 mesh and diamond paste. The polished specimens were then coated with gold, before being inspected by scanning electron microscopy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Fatigue Damage Mechanism.

1.a. Woven fabric composites.

The fatigue damage assessment of both knitted and woven fabric composites was performed by scanning electron microscopy and acoustic emission. The selection of both techniques was based on the complex nature of fatigue damage in textile fabric composites. Cracks in traditional composites can be filled with liquid penetrants and hence can be evaluated by radiography. However, the complexity of the damage shape in textile composites will be an obstacle in a correct filling with liquid penetrant for radiographic inspection. Therefore, the fatigue damage development in textile composites is difficult to be investigated with this technique.

The acoustic emission (AE) technique is the only in situ non-destructive technique which can be applied to detect damage when it develops while the experiment is being loaded. The major damage types in fiber reinforced composite materials, such as fiber fracture, matrix cracking, matrix-fiber debonding, and delamination, will produce AE signals. The major disadvantage of AE is that great skill is needed in order to correlate the AE data with the particular damage mechanisms in a material. The interpretation of AE signals coming from different damage types is not straightforward. In order to facilitate this AE interpretation, researchers often compare AE data with other damage characterization techniques (ultrasonic C-scan, radiography and scanning electron microscopy).

Microscopic techniques such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM) have often been used to complement AE in the damage investigation. The main disadvantage of SEM is that the technique is destructive. It means that an investigated specimen can only be subjected until a certain damage level or number of fatigue cycles. The specimen then needs to be cut and analysed either at the edge of the specimen or over the cross-section. The use of AE provides information (event rate or amplitude of AE) before the fatigue test is stopped and the specimen is evaluated microscopically.

Figure 1 shows the AE event rate of a woven fabric composite subjected to a maximum fatigue load ratio S_{max} of 0.5. Based on the AE analysis, accompanied with the SEM investigation, tensile fatigue damage at this fatigue load can be classified into 4 stages. In the first stage, no AE activities were recorded. It means that there is no fatigue damage in specimen yet in the area monitored with AE. This is not true for the whole specimen because the woven fabric composite has been subjected to a tensile load higher than the knee point of the stress-strain curve of this composite. (The knee point is the transition point between the linear and non-linear stress-strain relationship) Damage in the material is indicated by the non-linear relationship in the stress-strain curve. It could be the AE signal of the first damage is too weak and is damped before reaching the sensors. In this paper, the AE evaluation covered only 30 % of the total area. AE sensors were also located at the middle of the specimen and far from the grip to avoid grip noise detection.

The first AE event from the monitored region is detected at 12.000 cycles. At this moment, the second stage begins. A complementary fatigue test on another sample was performed and stopped at 15000 cycles where the second stage has already been reached. From the SEM inspection, fatigue damage at this stage consists of fiber-matrix debonds and matrix cracks in transverse yarns. Both fiber matrix debonds and matrix cracks in the transverse yarn are observed as a continuous transverse crack. The AE amplitude of the AE events at the second stage is mainly between 45 and 50 dB. Some references reported that the amplitude in this range can be contributed to matrix cracks [9,10]. This transverse bundle crack subsequently grows either into a rich-matrix area or is deflected by the longitudinal fiber bundle within the

same layer (meta-delamination, see figure 2). Another complementary fatigue test, which was stopped at 40.000 cycles and still in the second stage, showed transverse cracks and meta-delaminations in the specimen. Because both transverse cracks and meta-delaminations occur in the same stage, it was difficult to discern AE events which can result from either a meta-delamination or a transverse crack. Based on the first and second complementary fatigue tests, the AE amplitude of meta-delamination was predicted to be around 50-55 dB or higher than the AE amplitude of transverse crack. All the transverse yarns in the woven fabric composite are sensitive to transverse cracks. Therefore, accumulative AE events grow rapidly until all transverse yarns are damaged.

Figure 1. AE result of woven fabric composite subjected to a maximum fatigue load ratio S_{max} of 0.5

If all transverse yarns are already damaged, the propagation of the transverse crack proceeds very slowly. Therefore less AE events were recorded. This condition was defined as the third stage. There seems to be a delay between the initial damage and the final failure (the fourth stage), because the final failure is strongly determined by the failure in the longitudinal yarn. However, the initial failure takes place mostly in the transverse yarn that gives a small contribution to the total strength and stiffness. At the beginning of the third stage, the stiffness is still around 90% of the original value. For unnotched specimens, the final failure can take place randomly in the whole specimen. If the final failure occurs not in the investigated AE area (between the two AE sensors), AE data resulting from the final failure can not be recorded. The AE measurement will end at stage 3. Many unnotched specimens failed at the area close to the gripping device. This is due to the high stress concentrations around the gripping device. End tabs were used to reduce the stress concentration close to grips and hence reduce the failure in the grips. Figure 1 shows a complete AE measurement on the fatigued woven fabric composite, because the final failure takes place at the investigated area. A lot of events with AE amplitudes higher than 60 dB were recorded at the final failure stage. These amplitudes are contributed by fiber fracture. Figure 2 shows a scheme of the tensile fatigue damage development in woven fabric composites.

The fatigue damage development is strongly influenced by the maximum fatigue load ratio S_{max} . At high fatigue loads ($S_{max} = 0.7$), the fatigue damage development is more continuously instead of stepwise like the fatigue damage development for $S_{max} = 0.5$. The localisation of fatigue damage, where the final failure takes place for $S_{max} = 0.7$, occurs faster than for $S_{max} = 0.5$. However, at a maximum fatigue load ratio S_{max} lower than 0.5, the fatigue damage development consists of more stages. Transverse cracks and meta-delaminations can occur at different fatigue damage stages. Therefore, AE information such as the AE amplitude of meta-delaminations can give more detail.

Figure 2. Scheme of the tensile fatigue damage development on woven fabric composites

1.b. Knitted fabric composites.

The fiber orientation distribution of knitted fabric composites is substantially different from that of woven fabric composites. The fiber geometry represents a more 3-dimensional structure with curved fiber bundles, as shown on figure 3. The fatigue failure is initiated by fiber-bundle debonds at bundles that are located perpendicular to the tensile fatigue loading. The propagation of the debonds was strongly influenced by the orientation of the fiber bundles. The orientation in one fiber bundle varies from one place to other place. The propagation of the debonds was faster at the part of the fiber bundles whose orientation is perpendicular to the fatigue loading. The propagation slowed down, because the orientation of the fiber bundle moved from a perpendicular to a parallel direction with respect to the fatigue loading. The debonds then grew very slowly or stopped at an area whose fiber direction is parallel to the fatigue loading. A continuous crack over two fiber bundles could be created if the debond jumped to another fiber bundle that had been damaged by a debond as well.

Figure 3. Structure and fatigue damage type of knitted fabric composites, subjected to a maximum fatigue load ratio S_{\max} of 0.5 in wale direction.

Figure 4 shows the AE event rate of knitted fabric composites subjected to a maximum fatigue load ratio S_{\max} of 0.5 in wale direction. In the middle of the specimen, the first AE event was detected at the beginning of the fatigue cycles. Based on the AE event pattern, the fatigue damage development in the middle was classified into 2 stages.

The first stage is the initial fatigue damage stage in which knitted fabric composites have been damaged by debonding. The debonding occurred randomly in the specimen, but perpendicular to the fatigue loading direction. Debonding of one fiber bundle can jump to an adjacent fiber bundle resulting in either a new debonding or a continuous debonding. In this kind of debonding propagation, fatigue damage failure can be concentrated in a particular part of the specimen. As a consequence, that part will be weak and critical. The localised fatigue damage stage is defined as the third or final failure stage that started at 48.500 fatigue cycles.

Figure 4. AE result of a knitted fabric composite subjected to a maximum fatigue load ratio S_{max} of 0.5 in wale direction.

2. Fatigue life, Residual Stiffness and Residual Strength.

Based on the nature of fatigue damage, knitted fabric composites were expected to have a lower fatigue resistance compared to woven fabric composites. In this paper, the fatigue resistance will be discussed in terms of fatigue life, residual stiffness, and residual strength. Fatigue life can be studied from the S-N curve, as shown on figure 5. Woven and knitted fabric composites have a comparable fatigue life. In other words, the propagation of the fiber bundle debonding can be slowed down or stopped by a complex structure of knitted fabrics where parts of fiber bundles are oriented in the fatigue loading direction and hence they can hold the load.

Figure 5. S-N curve of knitted and woven fabric composites

The stiffness degradation in knitted fabric composites is more severe than in woven fabric composites. The decrease in the stiffness of knitted fabric composites is strongly dominated by the quality of the fiber-matrix interface, where the fatigue damage is initiated. Therefore, the stiffness of knitted fabric composites decreases rapidly when the number and/or the length of the fiber bundle debonds increase, as shown in figure 6. In woven fabric composites, the stiffness of the transverse fiber bundles, at which fatigue damage is initiated, only gives a small contribution to the total stiffness (less than 10 %). Hence, with respect to the stiffness degradation, knitted fabric composites show a lower fatigue resistance tolerance than woven fabric composites. The fatigue damage at the beginning of the fatigue test, resulting in stiffness degradation, was not detected by AE measurement. The fatigue damage might occur not in the AE investigated area. It is however more probable that the first AE signals are too weak and are damped before they reach the sensors.

Static tensile tests at different fatigue intervals were performed to investigate the residual tensile strength of the fatigued specimen. Figure 7 shows the residual strength of woven and knitted fabric composites subjected to maximum fatigue load ratio of $S_{max} = 0.5$. Knitted fabric composites have slightly higher fatigue resistance than woven fabric composites. The propagation of cracks and debondings in knitted fabric composites was perturbed by a complex structure of knitted fabric.

Figure 6. Stiffness degradation in woven and knitted fabric composites, subjected to a maximum fatigue load ratio of $S_{max} = 0.5$.

Figure 7. Residual strength of woven and knitted fabric composites subjected to a maximum fatigue load ratio of $S_{\max} = 0.5$.

CONCLUSIONS

The tensile fatigue damage development in plain weave and knitted fabric composites has been studied. Fatigue damage in plain-weave fabric composites was characterized by cracks in the transverse fiber bundles. Stiffness and strength decreased slightly when the fatigue cycles increase, because transverse fiber bundles give only a small contribution to the total mechanical properties. Fatigue damage in knitted fabric composites was characterized by fiber-matrix debonding in the part of the fiber bundles with a direction perpendicular to the fatigue loads. As all fiber bundles in knitted fabric composites can be damaged by debonding, mechanical properties such as stiffness will decrease faster than in woven fabric composites at the same normalized fatigue life. With respect to residual stiffness, woven fabric composites show a better fatigue resistance than knitted fabric composites. However, both woven and knitted fabric composites give comparable results in the fatigue life and the residual strength.

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